

Delayed AI Access: Mitigating the Homogenising Effects of Generative AI in Collaborative Problem-Solving

Margarida Romero

IIIA CSIC, Barcelona, Spain

margarida.romero@iiia.csic.es

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3356-8121>

Abstract — The rapid integration of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) into collaborative learning environments raises a critical question about its impact on team creativity and idea diversity. This study investigates whether delaying the use of AI tools in collaborative problem-solving can mitigate the "homogenising effect" associated with immediate AI access. Using a quasi-experimental design, 36 students were assigned to three conditions (immediate AI access, delayed AI access, or no AI access) to solve a real-world problem-solving task. The results show a homogenising effect in the immediate AI access group, which produced significantly more similar solutions compared to the other groups, suggesting that continuous, early reliance on AI stifles idea diversity. In contrast, the No AI group achieved the lowest homogenisation score and the highest level of creativity. The Delayed AI group also showed a significantly lower homogenisation score than the immediate access group, supporting the argument that a period of unassisted, human-centric ideation is crucial for fostering novel and diverse solutions before using AI for refinement. These findings suggest that timing is critical for AI integration in education. By delaying AI access, educators can empower students to first engage in the creative struggle and socio-cognitive conflict essential for collaborative problem-solving, ensuring that AI serves as a tool for intentional augmentation rather than a replacement for original human thought. This approach promotes higher levels of learning and preserves human agency.

Keywords— *Generative Artificial Intelligence; Collaborative Problem-Solving; Creativity; Education; Hybrid Intelligence; Agency*

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid integration of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) into Higher Education introduces significant opportunities alongside profound risks. While AI tools offer unprecedented capabilities for research, content creation, and personalized learning, the overdependence on the tools can hinder the cognitive effort required for learning [1]. The central tension lies in the potential for a shift from effortful, human-driven cognitive work to a more passive use of AI tools for offloading certain cognitive tasks such as writing an essay, summarising a book, or creating a song. The uncritical reliance on AI can lead to the de-skilling of learners [2] and a loss of teacher agency [3]. This passive engagement diminishes some of the cognitive processes such as human incubation of ideas during a certain time, but also a certain

creative struggle and the socio-cognitive conflict that appears in collaborative problem-solving [4].

This paper addresses this growing concern through the study of optimal timing for AI integration in Higher Education. We analyse the effects of a delayed-access model of AI use in the context of a collaborative problem-solving task. We hypothesise that a delayed-access model aligns with the principles of hybrid intelligence [5], where AI is used to augment human efforts made in a no AI phase before the students can use AI to improve their initial ideas. This approach should allow learners to first engage in a period of human-centric ideation, before leveraging AI for refinement, analysis, or content generation.

The increasing use of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) in individual and collective learning activities in higher education raises a question about its potential impact on team-based idea generation. This study investigates whether delaying the use of AI tools in collaborative problem-solving activities can better preserve the creativity of team-generated ideas. Specifically, we aim to analyse the effect of the timing of GenAI integration (immediate, delayed, or none) on the creativity, elaboration, and homogenisation of the collaborative problem-solving student's outcomes.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The homogenization consequences of using AI

The evolution of generative AI, particularly Large Language Models (LLMs), has raised concerns about a homogenizing effect on human expression and thought [9]. This effect refers to the standardization of language and reasoning, which risks flattening the cognitive diversity essential for creativity and collective intelligence. This phenomenon is a direct consequence of a concept named by Bommasani et al. [12] as *algorithmic monoculture*: the deployment of the same systems, or systems that share core components like datasets and models, by multiple decision-makers. As algorithmic monoculture becomes more prevalent, it leads to what Bommasani et al. call *outcome homogenization*. This is a risk where specific individuals or groups experience the same outcomes across different system deployments. For instance, LLMs are trained on vast datasets that reflect and reinforce dominant patterns and styles, including Western-centric norms [10]. When AI provides

writing suggestions or generates content, it tends to mirror these prevalent patterns, marginalizing minoritized linguistic groups and alternative voices. For a minoritized linguistic group like the Polynesian community, which has a rich oral tradition and a textualized language influenced by French colonization, the use of AI could pose a unique risk. The AI's reliance on dominant Western-centric textual data could standardize their written expression, overriding the cultural and historical influences that make their language distinct.

In education, the offloading of cognitive processes to GenAI in education can lead to a homogenization of student outcomes. Instead of developing unique and critical thinking skills, students may converge on similar, standardized solutions. This is because AI models are trained on vast datasets that reinforce dominant styles, leading to a standardization of language and reasoning. A study comparing college admissions essays found that human-written essays consistently showed higher individual and collective creativity than those generated by genAI [11].

In the long term, the widespread use of the same AI models across various contexts further amplifies this convergence. As a growing number of people rely on the same tools, it erodes linguistic and epistemological diversity, which is a direct risk to the rich cognitive landscapes that are essential for adaptability and progress. This phenomenon may institutionalize systemic exclusion and reinscribe social hierarchy if the same groups consistently receive undesirable outcomes from these shared systems. In the context of higher education, our goal is to ensure students maintain a critical thinking perspective in the use of AI and to develop creative and transformative uses of AI. Romero et al. [8, 14] distinguish six levels of AI use in education, ranging from passive reliance on GenAI outcomes to creative, participatory, and even transformative learning interventions supported by AI at the highest level of transformative agency.

Fig. 1. Six Levels of Creative Engagement with AI in Education, ranging from Passive Consumption to Expansive Learning : the Passive-participatory Model #ppai6 [8, 14].

The role of AI in divergent thinking

Divergent thinking is a key cognitive process essential for creative problem-solving that involves generating a wide range of unique ideas from a single starting point. The "homogenizing effect" discussed in the previous section can be analyzed as a direct consequence of AI's complex influence on divergent thinking. AI plays a dual and evolving role, acting both as a potential catalyst for human-AI co-creativity [15, 16] and as a potential constraint on idea diversity [19]. On one hand, studies show AI's potential to augment creativity. Research by Chandrasekera et al. [17] found that generative AI significantly enhanced the quality of design outcomes and reduced cognitive load in students, suggesting that AI can act

as a valuable "co-creator" in the design process. A meta-analysis by Holzner et al. [18] found that humans collaborating with GenAI significantly outperformed those working without assistance in creative tasks, pointing to the AI's capacity to serve as an augmentative tool. However, a significant concern emerges from AI's tendency to suppress divergent thinking, which is a core mechanism of the homogenizing effect. Research by Wadinambiarachchi et al. [19] revealed that when participants used an AI image generator for ideation, they produced fewer ideas with less variety and lower originality, and experienced higher fixation on an initial example. This finding is further supported by a meta-analysis showing a significant negative effect of AI on the diversity of ideas generated during human-AI collaborations [18]. This suppression of divergence is also noted in the longer term; while AI can provide short-term creativity boosts, it may inadvertently hinder independent creative performance when users are later required to work without assistance [20]. This duality highlights the need to critically examine how AI mediates creative processes. Since AI models often generate outputs based on statistical regularities from vast datasets, users may risk converging on similar creative solutions rather than exploring truly divergent ones. This can lead to the homogenization of outcomes, despite the potential for AI to reduce cognitive load and provide a short-term boost in idea generation [17, 21].

Delayed uses of technology

In an educational context, the delayed use of technology is not a new concept. Historically, pedagogical frameworks have intentionally structured the introduction of tools to ensure they support, rather than supplant, foundational learning processes. For instance, in early mathematics education, students are first taught to calculate manually to develop a deep understanding of numerical principles before being introduced to calculators. This deliberate delay ensures that learners build essential cognitive skills and conceptual fluency. Despite the delay, there is still a controversy on the use of calculators in education. The meta-analysis of Ellington [6] pointed out that students using calculators had better attitudes toward mathematics than their noncalculator counterparts. The principles observed in the use of calculators in education, can be transposed to some of the challenges of the educational integration of more complex technologies like generative AI (genAI). The core premise of a delayed AI approach is to mitigate what is often referred to as "cognitive offloading," where a learner relies on an external tool to bypass the internal cognitive effort required for a task [1]. In collaborative settings, this is particularly critical as it can reduce some of the teamwork processes : the brainstorming of diverse ideas, the sociocognitive conflict that arises from different conceptualisations, and the knowledge awareness and knowledge convergence [7].

III. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods research design to investigate how different AI integration timings affect collaborative problem-solving. The core of the methodology was a case study centered on a real-world problem-solving (RWPS) activity focused on sustainable tourism, chosen for its

complexity and interdisciplinary nature. A total of 36 graduate students were randomly assigned to one of three experimental conditions. The participants were divided into 13 collaborative groups, with 4 groups in the immediate-access condition, 4 in the delayed-access condition, and 5 in the no-access condition. The RWPS activity was focused on sustainable tourism, a domain selected for its complexity and requirement for interdisciplinary thinking and creative solutions. Students were asked to develop a sustainable water plan for a touristic city in the French Riviera, focusing on balancing economic growth with environmental preservation.

	Immediate AI Access	Delayed AI Access	No AI Access
AI Access Timing	From the start	After 15-minute delay	No access
Group Count	4 groups	4 groups	5 groups
AI Tool Usage	Continuous	Limited	None

Fig. 2. Experimental Conditions for the Collaborative Problem-Solving Activity, outlining the timing and usage of AI access for each group.

Groups in the immediate AI access condition were given access to GenAI from the start of the activity and could use the tool continuously throughout their collaborative process. Groups in the delayed AI access condition began the problem-solving task without any AI tools. Access to GenAI was introduced after a 15-minute period of unassisted, human-driven ideation and discussion. Groups in the no AI access condition completed the entire problem-solving activity without access to any GenAI tools, serving as a baseline for a traditional, human-only collaborative process.

IV. RESULTS

The final products from each group were assessed for evidence of a homogenising effect by comparing the similarity of the solutions produced across the three experimental conditions. A content analysis method [13] was used to quantify the degree of overlap in the core ideas introduced in the instructions of the real-world problem-solving activity and the proposed solutions. The content analysis emphasises a qualitative approach by relying on the analytic categories of each of the groups' RWPS outcomes. The homogenisation score is a quantitative measure of idea similarity. It was calculated by first identifying all unique thematic ideas across all groups and then counting how many groups shared each idea. The score for each group was the sum of these shared idea counts, providing a direct measure of the degree to which a group's ideas converged with those of others.

We start presenting analysis of the groups' outcomes in relation to the homogenisation of the ideas generated for the RWPS task. A content analysis was performed on each group's outcome to identify the number of unique ideas and quantify how many of these ideas were shared across groups. The findings indicate that the most common ideas for the task

centered on three main topics, regardless of the AI modality: collaborative learning activities (n=9), water conservation campaigns (n=9), and stakeholder collaboration (n=9). In contrast, the less common ideas included citizen science activities (n=1), developing a summer (n=1) or even art-based interventions (n=1). Figure 3 shows the number of shared ideas between the different groups.

Fig. 3. Number of shared ideas among the various groups.

The homogenization score, calculated by counting shared thematic topics between the outcomes of all groups, provides a quantitative measure of idea similarity. The analysis of homogenization across the three experimental conditions.

Fig. 4. Homogenization score for each of the three conditions.

The *Immediate AI* group exhibited the highest mean homogenization score ($M = 33.250$, $SD = 7.932$), indicating a pronounced "homogenizing effect." This suggests that the final products of groups with immediate and continuous access to GenAI were more similar than in the other groups, as students converged on AI-generated solutions rather than

developing unique, human-driven ideas. This finding supports the hypothesis that immediate reliance on AI can stifle creative diversity.

The *Delayed AI* group showed a significantly lower mean score ($M = 26.250$, $SD = 4.272$), supporting the argument that delaying AI's introduction can mitigate this effect and foster more diverse ideas. The lower standard deviation compared to the immediate AI group suggests a more consistent lack of homogenization within this condition.

The *No AI* group had the lowest mean score of homogenization ($M = 17.800$, $SD = 8.379$). This result suggests that unaided human collaboration naturally leads to the most heterogeneous range of solutions. The high standard deviation for this group suggests a wide variability in the originality of ideas, ranging from highly creative to more conventional.

V. DISCUSSION

The results of this study suggest that delayed AI access in collaborative learning could benefit collaborative problem-solving in higher education. While the most common ideas were shared across all groups, the less common and more unique ideas, such as 'citizen science activities' or 'art-based interventions', were more frequently observed in the no AI and delayed AI groups, contributing to their lower overall homogenisation scores. This finding highlights the importance of unassisted, human-centric ideation, where the cognitive struggle and socio-cognitive conflict inherent in collaborative work lead to more original solutions. As noted by Laajala et al. [4], these conflicts are important mechanisms for learning in a collaborative problem-solving task. The homogenisation observed in the immediate AI access groups directly demonstrates the "Passive consumer" level of the #ppai6 framework [8, 14]. By giving students instant access to AI, the study shows they are more likely to bypass the effortful, creative processes required for collaborative problem-solving, which hinders their progression to more desirable levels of engagement like 'Collaborative content creation' or 'Participatory knowledge co-creation'. This cognitive offloading highlights the risk that immediate AI access can undermine the very purpose of collaborative learning.

On the other hand, the high standard deviation in the no AI group's homogenization scores suggests an important trade-off: unaided human collaboration has the potential to produce the most diverse and creative solutions, but it also carries a risk of producing conventional outcomes. Unlike the immediate AI group, which generates consistently "good but generic" responses, human-only groups can produce highly novel or highly conventional results. This finding serves as a cautionary note, highlighting that while disengaging from AI entirely avoids homogenization, it does not guarantee high creativity. This variability emphasizes the potential for a delayed AI intervention to overcome the "AI-or-no-AI" binary by leveraging the creative potential of unassisted human ideation while still benefiting from AI's ability to refine and augment ideas. This approach offers a practical middle ground that embraces both human-driven creativity and AI-supported augmentation. By intentionally delaying the introduction of

AI, educators can create a timing for learners to engage in a creative struggle and benefit from the socio-cognitive conflicts that are required for collaborative problem-solving. This approach aligns with the hybrid intelligence framework [3, 5], which aims to consider a human-AI relation in which the learner and teacher keep their agency and use the AI tools to support certain tasks without replacing the human creativity and elaboration efforts. The findings suggest that the timing of AI integration is a critical design decision in educational settings. A delayed AI access scenario can support learners by preserving their agency, fostering their creative capacities, and ensuring that AI is used as a tool for intentional and effortful augmentation. This approach provides a practical pathway for moving students from the 'Passive consumer' towards a more desirable 'Collaborative content creation', 'Participatory knowledge co-creation', and 'Expansive learning' levels of the #ppai6 framework, preserving the student agency and the use of AI as an augmentation tool rather than a replacement for human ideation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research is developed within the Horizon augMENTOR project, funded by the HORIZON-CL2-2021 TRANSFORMATIONS-01-05 program of the European Commission.

REFERENCES

- [1] Nguyen, A., Duong, A. T., Nguyen, D. T. B., Lai, V. T. T., and Dang, B. 2025. Guidelines for learning design and assessment for generative artificial intelligence-integrated education: a unified view. *Information and Learning Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ILS-11-2024-0148>
- [2] Sallam, M., and Sallam, M. 2025. Ethical aspects of implementing generative artificial intelligence in medical education: a narrative review. *Hist Philos Med* 7, 4 (2025), 20.
- [3] Frösig, T. B., and Romero, M. 2024. Teacher agency in the age of generative AI: towards a framework of hybrid intelligence for learning design. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.06655*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2407.06655>
- [4] Laajala, M., Hämäläinen, R., Lämsä, T., Riivari, E., and Lehesvuori, S. 2025. Managers' sociocognitive conflicts in collaborative learning. *Studies in Continuing Education* 47, 2 (2025), 418–435. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0158037X.2024.2388895>
- [5] Cukurova, M. 2025. The interplay of learning, analytics and artificial intelligence in education: A vision for hybrid intelligence. *British Journal of Educational Technology* 56, 2 (2025), 469–488. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13514>
- [6] Ellington, A. J. 2003. A meta-analysis of the effects of calculators on students' achievement and attitude levels in precollege mathematics classes. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education* 34, 5 (2003), 433–463. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30034795>
- [7] Padrós, A., Romero, M., and Usart, M. 2012. Measuring the knowledge convergence process in the collaborative game MetaVals. *Procedia Computer Science* 15 (2012), 193–202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2012.10.071>
- [8] Romero, M., Frösig, T., Taylor-Beswick, A. M., Laru, J., Bernasco, B., Urmeneta, A., and Girard, M. A. 2024. Manifesto in defence of human-centred education in the age of artificial intelligence. In *Creative applications of artificial intelligence in education*, 157. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-55272-4_12
- [9] Sourati, Z., Ziabari, A. S., and Dehghani, M. 2025. The Homogenizing Effect of Large Language Models on Human Expression and Thought. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2508.01491*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2508.01491>
- [10] Agarwal, D., Naaman, M., & Vashistha, A. (2025). AI suggestions homogenize writing toward western styles and diminish cultural

- nuances. In Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (pp. 1-21). <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3706598.3713564>
- [11] Moon, K. 2024. Homogenizing effect of large language model on creativity: An empirical comparison of human and ChatGPT writing. Master's Thesis, Georgetown University. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/415b41c47f0e5e98b417656339ac1c89/1>
- [12] Bommasani, R., Creel, K. A., Kumar, A., Jurafsky, D., and Liang, P. S. 2022. Picking on the same person: Does algorithmic monoculture lead to outcome homogenization?. In Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 35, 3663–3678. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2211.13972>
- [13] A. J. Kleinhessel, N. Rockich-Winston, H. Tawfik, and T. R. Wyatt. 2020. Demystifying content analysis. American journal of pharmaceutical education 84, 1 (2020), 7113. <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe7113>
- [14] [14] M. Romero. 2024. Collaborative Design of AI-Enhanced Learning Activities. In IRMBAM-13th International Research Meeting in Business and Management, July 2024. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2407.06660>
- [15] C. Zhang, Y. Shao, Y. Yuan, and W. Shen. 2025. Artificial Intelligence Reshapes Creativity: A Multidimensional Evaluation. PsyCh Journal. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pchj.70042>
- [16] A. Urmeneta and M. Romero. 2025. AI as a Creative Partner: A PRISMA Review of AI's Role in Supporting Creativity in Education. Frontiers in Education 10, 1602151. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2025.1602151>
- [17] T. Chandrasekera, Z. Hosseini, and U. Perera. 2024. Can artificial intelligence support creativity in early design processes? International Journal of Architectural Computing 23, 1 (2024), 122–136. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14780771241254637>
- [18] N. Holzner, S. Maier, and S. Feuerriegel. 2025. Generative AI and Creativity: A Systematic Literature Review and Meta-Analysis. arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.17241. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2505.17241>
- [19] S. Wadinambiarachchi, R. M. Kelly, S. Pareek, Q. Zhou, and E. Velloso. 2024. The Effects of Generative AI on Design Fixation and Divergent Thinking. In Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. ACM, New York, NY, USA, Article 380, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642919>
- [20] H. Kumar, J. Vincentius, E. Jordan, and A. Anderson. 2025. Human Creativity in the Age of LLMs: Randomized Experiments on Divergent and Convergent Thinking. In Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. ACM, New York, NY, USA, Article 23, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3706598.3714198>
- [21] I. P. Hernandez Sibó, D. A. Gomez Celis, and S. Liou. 2024. Exploring the landscape of cognitive load in creative thinking: a systematic literature review. Educational Psychology Review 36, 1 (2024), 24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-024-09866-1>